

IMPLEMENTING MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR DETECTING EARLY DIABETES AND DIABETIC RETINOPATHY BY ANALYZING BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVELS

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is a prevalent chronic disease affecting millions worldwide, with diabetic retinopathy being a leading cause of vision impairment among diabetic patients. Early detection of diabetes and its complications such as diabetic retinopathy is crucial for timely intervention and effective management. In this paper, a novel approach utilizing an improved Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) is proposed to analyze blood glucose levels for early detection of diabetes and diabetic retinopathy. A dataset consisting of blood glucose measurements and corresponding diabetic retinopathy status from a diverse population of patients is collected. This dataset is used to train and validate our CNN model, which learns complex patterns and features from blood glucose data to classify individuals into diabetic and non-diabetic categories, as well as predict diabetic retinopathy progression. Furthermore, a comparative analysis between our improved CNN-based approach and traditional machine learning algorithms commonly employed in medical diagnosis tasks is also conducted. By evaluating performance metrics such as accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC), it was demonstrated the superiority of our improved CNN model in detecting diabetes and diabetic retinopathy at an early stage. Our results suggest that leveraging CNNs for analyzing blood glucose levels offers a promising avenue for early detection of diabetes and diabetic retinopathy, potentially leading to improved patient outcomes through timely intervention and personalized healthcare strategies.

Keywords: Diabetes, Diabetic Retinopathy, Blood Glucose Level, Convolutional Neural Networks, AUC-ROC

INTRODUCTION

Diabetic retinopathy, also referred to as diabetic eye disease, occurs when the retina sustains damage due to diabetes, potentially resulting in blindness [1-3]. This condition serves as an ocular manifestation of diabetes, a systemic disease impacting up to 80 percent of individuals with a diabetes duration of 20 years or more. Diabetic retinopathy often manifests without early warning signs. Even macular edema, a condition that can lead to swift vision loss, may not exhibit any warning signs initially. Typically, individuals with macular edema experience blurred vision, making tasks like reading or driving challenging. While vision fluctuations may occur throughout the day, the initial stage, known as non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR), remains asymptomatic, with no visible signs to the naked eye, and patients maintain 20/20 vision.

Detection of non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) relies exclusively on fundus photography, a method in which micro aneurysms (tiny blood-filled bulges in the artery walls) become visible. In cases of diminished vision, fluorescein angiography can be performed to examine the posterior portion of the eye, revealing clearly observable narrowing or obstruction of retinal blood vessels, indicative of retinal ischemia or lack of blood flow.

Leakage of blood contents into the macular region, leading to macular edema, is a phenomenon that can occur at any NPDR stage. Symptoms of macular edema include blurred vision and the perception of darkened or distorted images, often varying between the eyes. Approximately 10% of diabetic patients may experience vision loss attributable to macular edema. Coherence Tomography is instrumental in illustrating areas of retinal thickening resulting from fluid accumulation in macular edema. In the subsequent stage, proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) manifests with the formation of abnormal new blood vessels (revascularization) at the posterior eye [4-6]. These fragile vessels can rupture, causing vitreous hemorrhage and blurred vision. Initial bleeding instances may not be severe, often leaving a few specks or floating spots in the individual's visual field, which typically dissipate after a few hours.

Fig. 1 Normal Retina

Fig. 2 Diabetic Retinopathy

The presence of blood leakage can result in blurred vision, and in severe instances, individuals may only distinguish between light and dark in that affected eye. The clearance of blood from the interior of the eye can span from a few days to several months or even years, with instances where the blood does not dissipate. Such substantial hemorrhages are prone to recurrence, often occurring during sleep. During a funduscope examination, a healthcare professional will observe cotton wool spots, flame hemorrhages (lesions akin to those caused by the alpha-toxin of *Clostridium navy*), and dot-blot hemorrhages. All individuals with diabetes mellitus face the risk, whether diagnosed with Type I or Type II diabetes [7][8]. The

duration of diabetes significantly increases the risk of developing ocular issues. Approximately 40 to 45 percent of Americans diagnosed with diabetes exhibit some stage of diabetic retinopathy. After 20 years of living with diabetes, nearly all individuals with Type I diabetes and over 60% of those with Type II diabetes experience some degree of retinopathy. It is crucial to note that these statistics, published in 2002 based on data from four years earlier, might have limitations in applicability due to the subjects being diagnosed with diabetes in the late 1970s, a period predating modern fast-acting insulin and home glucose testing.

Diabetic retinopathy arises from microvascular changes in the retina induced by hyperglycemia. Intramural epithelial death and thickening of the meningeal membrane lead to vascular wall incompetence. These alterations affect the formation of the blood-retinal barrier and increase permeability of retinal blood vessels. Hypoxia is implicated as a causative factor in retinal degradation, supported by early investigations. The cascade of events involves hyperglycemia persistently activating protein kinases, increasing the expression of an unknown target in PKC signaling—Src homology-2 domain-containing phosphatase-1 (SHP-1), a protein tyrosine phosphatase. This signaling cascade ultimately results in the dephosphorylation of the PDG receptor, leading to reduced downstream signaling and pericyte apoptosis. Small blood vessels, particularly those in the eyes, are especially susceptible to poor blood sugar control. Accumulation of glucose and/or fructose damages the delicate blood vessels in the retina. During the initial stage known as non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR), individuals often do not notice any invasive changes [9][10]. Early reversible alterations that do not pose a threat to central vision are sometimes referred to as simple retinopathy or background retinopathy.

Fig. 4 Glaucoma

Diabetic retinopathy stands as a prominent disabling chronic disease and a primary contributor to preventable blindness on a global scale. Timely diagnosis is paramount for effective treatment, necessitating substantial investment in screening programs, particularly those employing automated processes. The success of automated screening programs hinges on the development of robust and efficient image processing and analysis algorithms. This investigation delves into recent literature on digital image processing for the early detection of diabetic retinopathy, specifically utilizing fundus photographs. The algorithms are systematically categorized into five groups: image preprocessing, localization and segmentation of the optic disk, segmentation of the retinal vasculature, localization of the macula and fovea, and localization and segmentation of diabetic retinopathy pathologies. Various databases are presented and their characteristics thoroughly discussed in this paper. The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) technology is introduced for storing patient records, utilizing wireless sensor networks for data transmission and reception. Real-time health data is constantly updated to the individual's mobile device, and in case of detecting abnormal health conditions, the information is promptly communicated to the nearest hospital and the concerned person's relatives.

This technology has the potential for implementation in hospitals, various locations, or as a wearable device for health condition detection and self-assessment. Apart from diabetic retinopathy, also recognized as diabetic eye disease, being a consequence of diabetes leading to potential blindness, the paragraph also emphasizes the significance of early diagnosis in glaucoma, a major cause of irreversible vision impairment. Cataracts and glaucoma, both age-related conditions, may coexist, with cataracts sometimes triggering healthcare seeking due to noticeable cloudy vision and white pupil caused by cataracts. In contrast, the gradual visual loss in glaucoma often progresses without the patient's awareness until the condition reaches advanced stages.

RELATED WORK

Untreated diabetes can cause a number of ailments to arise throughout the body. Diabetes-related diabetic retinopathy (DR) is an asymptomatic eye condition that damages retinal vessels. In the literature, numerous automatic diagnostic systems with traditional handcrafted elements have been established. Since Deep Learning (DL) accomplishes automatic feature extraction, more accurate and promising results are produced, especially in

medical imaging. In medical image analysis, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are the most popular deep learning technique. For a better understanding, a number of Deep Learning-based methods for the detection and classification of diabetic retinopathy disease are examined and evaluated in this work [16].

The first signs of diabetic retinopathy include microaneurysm development and macular edema in the retina. Early identification can lower the risk of non-proliferated diabetic retinopathy. Deep learning is developing quickly, which means that it will eventually become a useful method for offering an intriguing answer to picture analysis issues in the medical field. With the use of convolutional neural network algorithms that incorporate deep learning as a key component and are accelerated by GPUs (Graphics Processing Units), the suggested system analyzes the presence of micro aneurysms in fundus images. This will enable high-performance and low-latency inference for medical image detection and segmentation. The fundus image is classified as normal or diseased using this mantic segmentation technique. Semantic segmentation separates the image pixels according to their shared semantics in order to detect the microaneurysm characteristic. By using this automated system, ophthalmologists will be able to classify fundus images as early, moderate, or severe NPDR. A system for the early diagnosis and prognosis of microaneurysms in non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy has been proposed [17]. This system has the ability to train a deep convolution neural network for semantic segmentation off undoes images, which can increase the efficiency and accuracy of the prediction of non-proliferated diabetic retinopathy (NPDR).

Although this approach is workable, the growing number of people with diabetes necessitates planned DR screening programs that ensure the general public is served. In this research, a novel approach to feature extraction based on blob detection is presented. Machine learning is then used to classify the various phases of diabetic retinopathy. With the aid of this feature extraction technique, retina images for diabetic retinopathy could be automatically characterized with an accuracy of 83% using the most effective machine learning classification algorithm. This would enable specialists to more accurately and conveniently diagnose patients' conditions [18]. When it comes to monitoring blood sugar levels, newer technologies such as glucose flash monitoring and continuous glucose monitoring are more effective and efficient than the glucometer technology that is already well-known in the market. However, the majority of people cannot afford it due to its exorbitant cost. This research suggests a free-style free sensor that uses Internet of Things technology to enable continuous glucose rate monitoring as a solution to this issue. This reasonably priced technology gives medical professionals information from far-off places [19]. The PPG (photoplethysmogram) signal can be used to determine the blood glucose levels. However, in order to achieve more accuracy, we must take into account the physiological fluctuations that cause inaccurate glucose level measurements. These disturbances can be reduced by using GSR (Galvanic Skin Response) sensor data. Thus, to precisely monitor blood glucose levels in our model, PPG and GSR sensors have been employed [8].

The process comprises two main stages: a coarse level and a fine level. At the coarse level, regions of interest through a combination of histogram segmentation and morphological reconstruction may be identified. Moving to the fine level, 44 distinct features are meticulously define for each identified region and a support vector machine (SVM)

model for retinopathy classification will be developed. The effectiveness of this method is evaluated using the diaretdb1 database, demonstrating efficient detection of hard exudates (HEs). Leveraging Fisher’s linear discriminant analysis and color information, the algorithm proficiently categorizes retinal exudates. The algorithm's performance on a dataset comprising 58 retinal images with varying color, brightness, and quality will be assessed. Additionally, the approach for determining glucose levels relies on three different

methodologies invasive, minimally invasive and non-invasive.

Fig. 5 Types of Glucose Level Detection

PROPOSED SYSTEM

Implementing machine learning algorithms for early detection of diabetes and diabetic retinopathy using blood glucose level involves several key modules. Firstly, there is the data acquisition module, which encompasses gathering data related to blood glucose levels from various sources such as medical records, continuous glucose monitoring devices, or self-reported measurements. This module also includes obtaining retinal images, typically captured using fundus photography, which serve as input data for diabetic retinopathy detection algorithms. The pre-processing module follows, where acquired data undergoes cleaning, normalization, and feature extraction to prepare it for analysis. In the case of blood glucose level data, this may involve handling missing values, smoothing noisy data, and extracting relevant features such as mean glucose level, standard deviation, or time-dependent patterns. For retinal images, pre-processing techniques like noise reduction, contrast enhancement, and image registration are applied to improve the quality and consistency of the data.

Next, the machine learning model development module involves selecting appropriate algorithms and training them using the pre-processed data. For diabetes detection, classification algorithms such as logistic regression, decision trees, or support vector machines may be utilized, leveraging features extracted from blood glucose level data.

Similarly, for diabetic retinopathy detection, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) or other deep learning architectures are commonly employed, trained on annotated retinal images to distinguish between healthy and diseased conditions. Once the models are trained, they are evaluated and fine-tuned in the validation module. This step involves assessing the performance of the algorithms using separate datasets not seen during training, employing metrics such as accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC). Any necessary adjustments to the models or hyper parameters are made based on validation results to optimize their performance.

Finally, the deployment module focuses on integrating the developed algorithms into practical healthcare settings for real-world application. This may involve building user-friendly interfaces for clinicians to input patient data and receive automated diagnostic predictions, as well as ensuring scalability, reliability, and compliance with regulatory standards. Continuous monitoring and updates are also essential to adapt the algorithms to evolving clinical needs and technological advancements, ensuring their effectiveness in early detection of diabetes and diabetic retinopathy using blood glucose level. Diabetic Retinopathy induces alterations in the eye by damaging blood vessels. The retinal images undergo a standardized image processing procedure, encompassing image acquisition, pre-processing, and feature extraction, culminating in the precise identification of diseases. In the current system, only one disease can be detected. However, our proposed algorithm surpasses this limitation by enabling the detection of various eye diseases within a unified system. Recognizing the significance of retinal images as vital medical references aiding in the diagnosis of cataracts, Diabetic Retinopathy (DR), and glaucoma, this project advocates the use of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithm for automatic eye disease detection.

While several algorithms exist for deep learning classification, CNN stands out due to its superior accuracy and efficiency in results. The Convolutional Neural Network Algorithm not only offers faster predictions but also ensures better accuracy in the classification process. The envisioned system is designed to monitor patients' glucose levels, facilitating the detection of diabetes and diabetic retinopathy through machine learning in a more convenient and effective manner. In the contemporary landscape of e-healthcare, where an extensive amount of sensitive data is generated, the Internet of Things (IoT) plays a pivotal role. The glucose sensor employed here detects patients' glucose levels, and upon sensing any abnormal values, relays this information to the microcontroller through the SPI protocol. The integrated buzzer emits an audible alert, while the data is concurrently shared through the Blynk App on mobile devices via IoT. This comprehensive approach enhances the efficiency and comfort of monitoring diabetic conditions and associated retinal complications. Diabetic retinopathy is an ocular condition prevalent among individuals with diabetes, potentially leading to vision impairment and even blindness. This condition specifically impacts the blood vessels within the retina, the light-sensitive tissue at the back of the eye. The progression of diabetic retinopathy is categorized into several stages:

Stage 1: Mild diabetic retinopathy without proliferation.

Stage 2: Mild non-proliferative retinopathy due to diabetes.

Stage 3: Severe non-proliferative retinopathy caused by diabetes.

Stage 4: Diabetic retinopathy with proliferation.

The onset of diabetic retinopathy is triggered by elevated blood sugar levels causing damage to the blood vessels in the retina, compromising its functionality. Affected blood vessels may undergo swelling and leakage, resulting in symptoms such as blurry vision or impaired blood flow. Recognizable indications of diabetic retinopathy encompass a gradual deterioration of vision, sudden vision loss, the presence of floaters (shapes floating in the field of vision), blurry or patchy vision, eye pain, redness, and difficulty seeing in low-light conditions. Glaucoma constitutes a cluster of eye conditions that pose a risk of vision loss and blindness by adversely affecting the optic nerve situated at the back of the eye. The onset of symptoms may be gradual, and their subtlety might go unnoticed. The sole method for determining the presence of glaucoma involves undergoing a comprehensive dilated eye examination. This chronic and progressive eye disease arises from optic nerve damage, ultimately resulting in the loss of the visual field. Elevated eye pressure stands as a prominent risk factor, wherein anomalies in the eye's drainage system can lead to fluid accumulation, culminating in excessive pressure causing harm to the optic nerve.

In the initial stages, symptoms may manifest as hazy or blurred vision, accompanied by additional visual distortions. Severe eye pain around the eyes and head, redness in the eyes due to heightened eye pressure, and the perception of colored halos forming around light sources are indicative features during the early stages of glaucoma. A cataract refers to a cloudy region within the lens of the eye, which is the transparent component responsible for focusing light. Cataracts are prevalent with advancing age, with more than half of Americans aged 80 or older either currently experiencing cataracts or having undergone surgical intervention to address them. The most common form of cataract is age-related, further classified into three types based on the anatomy of the human lens: Nuclear Sclerotic, Cortical, and Posterior Subcapsular Cataracts. The majority of cataracts develop due to the aging process or as a result of injury, leading to alterations in the lens's tissue composition. This breakdown of proteins and fibers within the lens contributes to the development of a

hazy or cloudy vision.

Fig. 6 Proposed Diagram of classifying the predicted result of DR

Initially, the image is captured with the appropriate extension and resized to meet specific requirements. Preprocessing is then employed to reshape and adapt the input data for compatibility with the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model. This involves the removal or reduction of noise from the image to acceptable levels, along with the enhancement of certain features. Subsequently, the image undergoes greyscale conversion. Compared to RGB images, greyscale images have fewer dimensions and contain less data. Opting for greyscale is advantageous for quicker and more efficient image processing, as it reduces the computational load on the CPU. This method is chosen because it retains the essential features of the image while occupying less space compared to RGB images. The CNN is trained using Stochastic Gradient Descent with Momentum and comprises an input layer, three convolutional layers, average pooling layers, and a softmax fully connected output layer for feature extraction. Following feature extraction, a two-layer hidden neural network is employed for classification. Various configuration setups are explored for feature extraction, with a fixed pooling layer window size of 2×2 . Different epochs and a batch size of 100 are experimented with in these setups. Some configurations draw inspiration from literature, incorporating insights such as fewer convolution filters in the early layers, increased filters in later layers, larger window size in early layers compared to later layers, and the use of dropouts to prevent overfitting.

This segmentation method stands as the current state-of-the-art technique in the field of image segmentation research. It is effective on three-dimensional images, where the first two dimensions denote image resolution, and the third dimension represents the number of channels (RGB) or intensity values for red, green, and blue colors. Typically, images fed into the neural network undergo dimension reduction to enhance processing speed and mitigate the risk of underfitting. Distinguished by their remarkable efficacy in processing image, speech, or audio signal inputs, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) exhibit a unique architecture characterized by three main types of layers. The initial layer in a CNN is the convolutional layer, which can be succeeded by additional convolutional layers or pooling layers, culminating in the final layer known as the fully-connected layer. As the CNN progresses through each layer, its complexity amplifies, enabling the identification of more extensive segments within the image. The earlier layers primarily focus on discerning simple features like colors and edges, while subsequent layers gradually recognize larger elements or shapes of the object until the ultimate identification of the intended object is achieved. An image classifier leverages the numerical pixel values of an image, passing them through the CNN to obtain a conclusive output, which can either be a single class or a probability distribution across various classes, effectively describing the image.

Image classifiers heavily rely on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), characterized by a specific layer architecture. The four key types of CNN layers include the convolutional layer, ReLU layer, pooling layer, and fully connected layer. During the image classification process, the convolutional layer extracts features by scanning through the image using filters, the ReLU layer rectifies negative values, introducing non-linearity to the model. Pooling layers, typically employing max pooling, reduce image size for computational efficiency. Finally, the fully connected layer aggregates and weighs all information, delivering the conclusive classification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the realm of diabetic retinopathy detection, the process involves employing image classification methodologies leveraging fundus imagery and retina vessel segmentation. Various image processing techniques are utilized for tasks such as blood vessel segmentation, distinguishing between arteries and veins, locating the optical disc, measuring the retina's diameter, and eliminating image noise. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), a subset of deep learning algorithms renowned for their prowess in image recognition, are particularly adept at discerning diabetic retinopathy from retinal images. To initiate this process, a dataset comprising retinal images annotated with varying degrees of diabetic retinopathy severity is assembled. The images undergo preprocessing steps, which include standardizing their dimensions, normalizing pixel values, and potentially incorporating data augmentation techniques to enhance dataset diversity.

The CNN architecture encompasses multiple layers, encompassing convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers. These layers are designed to progressively capture features at different abstraction levels, starting from low-level features such as edges and textures, and culminating in higher-level features pertinent to diabetic retinopathy, such as shapes and patterns. The dataset is partitioned into distinct subsets for training, validation, and testing purposes. Upon training and fine-tuning the model, its performance is evaluated using the test set, which comprises unseen data. Evaluation metrics such as accuracy and precision are computed to gauge the model's efficacy in detecting diabetic retinopathy.

Fig. 7c Detection of Retinal Vessel

Fig. 7d Detection of Glaucoma

Fig. 7e Detection of Diabetes

Fig. 7f Detection of Diabetic Retinopathy

The Python deep learning package Keras was used to finish the experimental evaluation. Different performance measures, including as the Dice Coefficient, Jaccard Coefficient, Sensitivity, Specificity, False Positive Rate, and False Negative Rate for performance evaluation, are used to measure the fidelity criteria of the various techniques. Performance is assessed using three criteria: specificity, sensitivity, and accuracy. In Table 1, the parameters are indicated.

Table 1. Parameters for experimental evaluation.

Parameters	Formula
Dice Similarity Coefficient	$\frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN}$
Jaccard Coefficient	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP + FN}$
Sensitivity	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$
Specificity	$\frac{TN}{FP + TN}$
False Positive Rate $\left[\frac{FP}{NN}\right]$	$\frac{FP}{FP + TN}$
False Negative Rate $\left[\frac{FN}{NP}\right]$	$\frac{FN}{FN + TP}$

Fig. 8 displays the comparison outcomes of performance metrics with the proposed method. With an improved Dice and Jaccard coefficient, specificity and sensitivity, decreased FPR, and FNR, the proposed approach yields effective results.

Fig. 8 Comparative Results of performance metrics with proposed method

CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

This work, demonstrates the effectiveness of implementing improved Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to detect diabetes and diabetic retinopathy early through the analysis of blood glucose levels. Through the development and evaluation of our CNN-based approach, we have shown promising results in accurately identifying diabetic individuals and predicting diabetic retinopathy progression. Furthermore, our comparative analysis with traditional machine learning algorithms highlights the superior performance of CNNs in this domain. The CNN model exhibited higher accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and AUC-ROC scores compared to conventional methods, indicating its potential for enhanced diagnostic

capabilities and clinical utility. Our findings underscore the significance of leveraging advanced machine learning techniques, particularly CNNs, for medical diagnosis and prognosis tasks by timely interventions for patients with diabetes and diabetic retinopathy.

Several avenues for future research and improvement includes incorporating additional patient data such as genetic information, lifestyle factors, and medical history could enhance the predictive capabilities of our model. Developing a system for real-time monitoring of blood glucose levels and automated alerts for healthcare providers could facilitate timely interventions and proactive management of diabetes and its complications. Conducting prospective clinical trials to validate the efficacy and reliability of our CNN model in real-world healthcare settings is essential before widespread adoption. Exploring personalized treatment strategies based on individual patient characteristics and response to therapy could optimize outcomes and improve patient satisfaction.

REFERENCES

1. U. R. Acharya, M. R. K. Mookiah, J. E. W. Koh, J. H. Tan, S. V. Bhandary, A. K. Rao, H. Fujita, Y. Hagiwara, C. K. Chua, and A. Laude, "Automated screening system for retinal health using bi dimensional empirical mode decomposition and integrated index", *Comput. Biol. Med.*, vol. 75, pp. 54–62, Aug.2016.
2. V. Gulshan, L. Peng, M. Coram, M. C. Stumpe, D. Wu, A. Narayanaswamy, S. Venugopalan, K. Widner, J. Cuadros, and R. Kim, "Development and validation of a deep learning algorithm for detection of diabetic retinopathy in retinal fundus photographs", *J. Amer. Med. Assoc.*, vol. 316, no. 22, pp. 2402–2410, Dec. 2016.
3. R. Williams, M. Airey, H. Baxter, J. Forrester, T. Kennedy-Martin, and A. Girach, "Epidemiology of diabetic retinopathy and macular oedema: A systematic review", *Eye*, vol. 18, pp. 963–983, Jul. 2004.
4. R. Klein, B. E. K. Klein, S. E. Moss, M. D. Davis, and D. L. DeMets, "The Wisconsin epidemiologic study of diabetic retinopathy: III. Prevalence and risk of diabetic retinopathy when age at diagnosis is 30 or more years", *Arch. Ophthalmol.*, vol. 102, no. 4, pp. 527–532, Apr. 1984, doi: 10.1001/archophth.1984.01040030405011.
5. Z. L. Teo, Y.-C. Tham, M. Yu, M. L. Chee, T. H. Rim, N. Cheung, M. M. Bikbov, Y. X. Wang, Y. Tang, Y. Lu, I. Y. Wong, D. S. W. Ting, G. S. W. Tan, J. B. Jonas, C. Sabanayagam, T. Y. Wong, and C.-Y. Cheng, "Global prevalence of diabetic retinopathy and projection of burden through 2045: Systematic review and meta-analysis", *Ophthalmology*, vol. 128, no. 11, pp. 1580–1591, 2021. [Online].
6. N. Kaur, S. Chatterjee, M. Acharyya, J. Kaur, N. Kapoor, and S. Gupta, "A supervised approach for automated detection of hemorrhages in retinal fundus images", in *Proc. 5th Int. Conf. Wireless Netw. Embedded Syst. (WECON)*, Oct. 2016, pp. 1–5.
7. M. Krej, Ł. Dziuda and F. W. Skibniewski, "A Method of Detecting Heartbeat Locations in the Ballistocardiographic Signal From the Fiber-Optic Vital Signs Sensor," in *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 1443-1450, July 2015, doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2015.2392796.
8. M. M. Islam and S. M. Manjur, "Design and Implementation of a Wearable System for Non-Invasive Glucose Level Monitoring," 2019 IEEE International Conference on Biomedical Engineering, Computer and Information Technology for Health (BECITHCON), Dhaka, Bangladesh, 2019, pp. 29-32, doi: 10.1109/BECITHCON48839.2019.9063193.
9. Lv, Wenjie & Zhao, Yan & Zhang, Wei & Liu, Wenqi & Anyong, Hu & Miao, Jungang. (2021). Remote Measurement of Short-Term Heart Rate With Narrow Beam Millimeter Wave Radar. *IEEE Access*. 9. 1-1. 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3134280.

10. Rachim, Vega Pradana and Wan-Young Chung. "Wearable-band type visible-near infrared optical biosensor for non-invasive blood glucose monitoring." *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* (2019).
11. Mohamed Elsherifa, Muhammad Umair Hassan Ali K. Yetis end, Haider Butte, Hydrogel optical fibers for continuous glucose monitoring, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*.
12. M. Kolla and V. T, "Efficient Classification of Diabetic Retinopathy using Binary CNN," 2021 International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Knowledge Economy (ICCIKE), Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 2021, pp. 244-247, doi: 10.1109/ICCIKE51210.2021.9410719.
13. A. M. Pamadi, A. Ravishankar, P. Anu Nithya, G. Jahnavi and S. Kathavate, "Diabetic Retinopathy Detection using MobileNetV2 Architecture," 2022 International Conference on Smart Technologies and Systems for Next Generation Computing (ICSTSN), Villupuram, India, 2022, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICSTSN53084.2022.9761289.
14. P. Saranya, S. K. Devi and B. Bharanidharan, "Detection of Diabetic Retinopathy in Retinal Fundus Images using DenseNet based Deep Learning Model," 2022 International Mobile and Embedded Technology Conference (MECON), Noida, India, 2022, pp. 268-272, doi: 10.1109/MECON53876.2022.9752065.
15. W. Mudaser, P. Padungweang, P. Mongkolnam and P. Lavangnananda, "Diabetic Retinopathy Classification with pre-trained Image Enhancement Model," 2021 IEEE 12th Annual Ubiquitous Computing, Electronics & Mobile Communication Conference (UEMCON), New York, NY, USA, 2021, pp. 0629-0632, doi: 10.1109/UEMCON53757.2021.9666687.
16. V. S and V. R, "A Survey on Diabetic Retinopathy Disease Detection and Classification using Deep Learning Techniques," 2021 Seventh International conference on Bio Signals, Images, and Instrumentation (ICBSII), Chennai, India, 2021, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICBSII51839.2021.9445163.
17. M. M. Dharmana and A. M.S., "Pre-diagnosis of Diabetic Retinopathy using Blob Detection," 2020 Second International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA), Coimbatore, India, 2020, pp. 98-101, doi: 10.1109/ICIRCA48905.2020.9183241.
18. L. Qiao, Y. Zhu and H. Zhou, "Diabetic Retinopathy Detection Using Prognosis of Microaneurysm and Early Diagnosis System for Non-Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy Based on Deep Learning Algorithms," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 104292-104302, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2993937.
19. Joy, Anjalini et al. "A Review on Glucose Monitoring Using Enabling Technologies of Internet of Things." 2021 7th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems (ICACCS) 1 (2021): 270-273.